

A Packet Delay Emulator for High-Bandwidth and Low-Latency Traffic in 5G Networks

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Abstract—A Packet delay emulator for high bandwidth traffic is a specialized tool designed to simulate network delays and measure the impact on high-speed data transmission. Simulating network delays and measuring the impact on data transmission allows network administrators and developers to test their systems in a controlled environment, mimicking real-world scenarios with different network conditions. This paper discusses the limitations of traditional packet latency emulators and the technical considerations required to test high-speed networks, and proposes a specialized packet latency emulator to replicate real-world network conditions. Results compare the proposed emulator with the best tools that are currently available and show a performance in line with the reference, with a significant accuracy improvement in the presence of higher latencies.

Index Terms—5G networks, Packet delay emulation, Network performance testing.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant changes in the way research on the fifth-generation (5G) mobile networks [1] is conducted, compared to previous generations, is the increased utilization of prototype system implementations to explore various research ideas, rather than relying solely on simulations. The introduction of network slicing [2] has enabled the virtualization of networking infrastructure through the implementation of Network Function Virtualization (NFV) [3] and Software Defined Networking (SDN) [4]. NFV employs generic hardware to implement network functions instead of relying on application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs) designed for each function, resulting in the ability to create mobile networks using lower-cost hardware. This has attracted a great deal of attention from both industry and academia to experiment with new innovations. However, the implementation of these prototype systems requires careful consideration. While this architecture provides network engineers with greater flexibility, if not developed carefully, it can result in a significant increase in packet processing time.

5G technology is designed to support a wide range of use cases with varying requirements for latency, throughput, and reliability. These use cases include applications such as autonomous vehicles, remote surgery, and industrial automation, which require extremely low latency and high reliability. A network delay emulator is essential in the design process of modern data center networks to identify the optimal combination of various networking technologies. In addition, a delay emulator can help engineers to optimize the network

performance by testing different network configurations and tuning parameters such as Quality of Service (QoS) and network slicing. This ensures that the network is optimized to meet the specific requirements of each use case and provides the best possible performance for end users. Therefore, a delay emulator plays a crucial role in ensuring that 5G networks can deliver the high-speed, low-latency, and reliable connectivity required to support a wide range of innovative applications and services. However, most of the current, software-based delay emulators encounter problems with packet forwarding efficiency when it comes to handling high-bandwidth communications or are not able to assign different latencies to specific packet stream, as well as changing latencies at runtime.

Considering the aforementioned constraints, this paper presents Slice-Emulator (SIEmu), a network delay emulator able to introduce delays on a per-slice basis. SIEmu is developed by using the Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) [5], a collection of drivers and libraries that enables fast packet processing in network devices such as Network Interface Cards (NICs) and supports the creation of high-speed packet networking applications. The proposed emulator is packaged as a Docker container and can be configured for different delays per slices'/streams' attributes in a bidirectional way. A set of experiments have been performed to assess the performance of SIEmu against the most efficient, DPDK-based available tool [6]. Results show that SIEmu can achieve the same performance level and even surpass in terms of accuracy when the introduced delays are above 100,000 μs .

The paper is organized as follows. Section II reports the state of the art, while Section III presents the structure of SIEmu. The evaluation is in Section IV, and conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Network delay emulation tools are generally divided into two categories, hardware-based and software-based emulators. Hardware-based emulation tools are hardware devices that sit between the network endpoints. They offer high-fidelity emulation and detailed reporting capabilities because they are made up of customized ASICs or FPGAs and operate at a highly precise rate even in very fast network topologies such as 10Gb or 100Gb Ethernet. For instance, GNet-1 [7], a hardware-based Ethernet network testbed, offers a precision of approximately 32 nanoseconds. Shunra VE [8] is another

hardware-based simulation environment that supports latency, packet loss, jitter, bandwidth congestion, and utilization. It supports up to thousands of nodes while it is very fast, but the package is quite costly and demands a robust network infrastructure to be operational. [9]

As a matter of fact, unfortunately, physical delay emulation tools can be very expensive to purchase and maintain, especially if they simulate a wide range of network conditions or support multiple platforms. Likewise, using them can be complex and requires specialized knowledge and skills. The truth behind this has compelled network engineers to design software-based network emulators. However, as most of these emulation tools are installed on multi-purpose hardware, they have the potential to create significant unintended delays if they are not developed carefully, which can degrade the performance of these systems.

Most of the software-based emulators use Linux kernel for processing packets. The most well-known examples of these systems are NetEm [10], OMNeT++ [11], DummyNet [12] and NIST Net [13] but all of them are using Operating System (OS) kernel to exert delays. In broad-bandwidth traffic used in today's standard networks, the performance of emulators that are based on the kernel of OS is not desirable. [6] DEMU solved this dependency by using DPDK. It directly interacts with NICs, which makes it very efficient for broadband traffic. Based on their evaluations, DEMU reduces the packet loss to 0% for 10Gb Ethernet. However, DEMU, like other software-based delay emulation tools, has certain limitations that need to be addressed.

Utilizing VLANs is an inseparable part of today's networks which helps network administrators to create a more efficient, secure, and flexible network that can meet the needs of users and applications. VLANs are necessary for network segmentation, security, broadcast control, scalability, and QoS. In NFV, multiple virtual networks can be created on top of the physical network infrastructure, with each network serving a specific network function, such as a firewall, load balancer, or routing. These virtual networks can be configured with multiple VLANs to create logical segmentation and isolation between different network functions. To better simulate real-world scenarios, different levels of delays should be exerted by the emulator between each pair of network functions. Therefore, the emulator must be equipped with the ability to add different levels of delays to separate packet streams based on their specific characteristics, such as VLAN tag, MAC address, destination IP address, and so forth.

Another vital requirement for any network delay emulation tool is having the ability to adjust the delay in real-time in the network. This capability allows the evaluation of various network scenarios in real-time, which is essential for testing and verifying network performance under different conditions. Without this feature, network engineers would have to stop and restart the emulator each time they want to change the delay, which is a time-consuming and inefficient process. Furthermore, real-time delay adjustments enable engineers to detect and respond to network issues as they occur, leading to

quicker troubleshooting and resolution of problems. DEMU, applies a constant level of delay to all packet streams, and this delay remains static until the emulator is stopped and manually reconfigured with a different delay value. This means that any changes to the delay must be made during a period of network downtime, and the entire system must be halted and restarted, causing a significant disruption to the system's normal operation. This limitation can impede the evaluation of different scenarios in real-time, which can affect the emulator's overall effectiveness. A delay emulator should have the flexibility to adjust the delay value in real-time, so that it can be calibrated and fine-tuned to ensure optimal performance of the network.

The aforementioned constraints served as the key motivators for the development of a network latency emulator specifically for our 5/6G testbed. [14] The developed emulator is inspired by DEMU on using DPDK and bypassing the operating system's kernel.

III. PROPOSED NETWORK DELAY EMULATOR

SIEmu is a software-based network delay emulator developed based on DPDK. DPDK is designed to enable packet processing at extremely high speeds, with low latency and minimal overhead. It provides a set of libraries and APIs that allow developers to write high-performance network applications that run in user space, rather than in kernel space. This enables to bypass the kernel networking stack and access the underlying hardware directly, resulting in lower latency, higher throughput, and better scalability. This capability allows us to decrease the level of unintended delays that are added to packet streams. The emulator employs various CPU cores for different tasks and these cores are reserved to prevent the operating system tasks from utilizing them.

Fig. 1 illustrates the architecture of SIEmu. "Rx Core" is responsible for managing the incoming traffic. It examines the received packet streams' attributes to determine the appropriate action to be taken on the packet. Subsequently, based on its characteristics, the packet will be forwarded to a "Delay Core" for further processing. The emulator assigns n dedicated delay cores to handle the delay for n different slices/traffic streams, aiming to segregate different traffic loads and improve processing time. If there is a requirement to modify any attribute such as the VLAN tag, it is the responsibility of this particular core to alter it to the output attributes based on the configuration.

Once the packet has been retained for the specified delay time, the CPU core then dispatches the packet to the "Tx Core", whose duty is to forward packets via the output NIC. It immediately transmits any incoming packet from all parallel cores to NIC1. Since the reverse flow operates similarly, it is not shown in the figure for the sake of clarity. To clarify, when a packet is received via NIC1, it enters the system, undergoes a delay based on the characteristics, and is transmitted to NIC0. Moreover, as indicated in Fig. 1, the Rx and Tx cores directly interact with the NICs, eliminating any potential delays caused by the Linux kernel.

Fig. 1: Architecture of proposed emulator.

Fig. 2: Network topologies supported by SIEmu

In addition to the aforementioned required CPU cores, the emulator utilizes a separate CPU core called "Update Settings Core", which is responsible for modifying the emulator's settings in real-time. In case of any configuration alteration requested by user, this core processes new configuration file and applies new settings to the system. Since this task is carried out simultaneously, without any disruption in emulator's performance, changes can be implemented seamlessly.

Based on Fig. 1, and keeping into account the presence of an additional pair of Rx and Tx cores for the reverse flow, the installation system needs a minimum of $n + 5$ available CPU cores to run the emulator for n unique delay levels. Here, we utilize the term "unique" since the emulator automatically allocates streams with a similar delay time to the same delay core, enabling us to support more distinct delays. If the host has multiple NIC pairs and sufficient free CPU cores, the configuration can be expanded by replicating more blocks similar to Fig. 1. This is advantageous in balancing traffic across different NIC pairs, resulting in decreased undesirable delays. In this scenario, the required number of CPU cores is calculated as $\sum_{i=1}^k (N_i + 5)$, where k is the number of NIC pairs the emulator is utilizing, and N_1, N_2, \dots, N_k are the distinct delay levels each block supports.

As mentioned before, SIEmu has the capability to modify packets' characteristics such as VLAN tag, allowing the output to be sent to the same network with different attributes. As demonstrated in Fig. 2, the system supports two distinct deployment configurations. In Fig. 2a, the source and destination networks are distinct, and the output VLAN can remain unchanged. Conversely, based on Fig. 2b, if the output is connected to the same network, the VLAN tag can be adjusted to the output VLAN tag specified in the configuration file.

Finally, we have packaged our application as a Docker

Fig. 3: The proposed emulator in a containerized environment.

container, allowing for seamless deployment and scaling on containerized environments. It can be managed using container orchestration tools such as Kubernetes, which simplifies scaling, monitoring, and management of the emulator. Fig. 3 illustrates this architecture. In this scenario, the delay emulator is packaged as a Docker image and installed on a Kubernetes cluster. Each application shown in the diagram can represent a Network Function (NF) that requires communication with other NFs. NFs are configured to send packets to the appropriate NIC (NIC0 or NIC1) of the emulator, depending on the direction of the flow. Once the emulator receives the packets, it adds the corresponding delay time and subsequently sends them to the output NIC based on the direction of the flow. To ensure optimal performance, it is necessary to reserve an adequate number of CPU cores for the emulator's container and directly assign two physical NICs to it. With support for Kubernetes, our proposed emulator can easily be deployed on any cloud provider or on-premises infrastructure. It can automatically scale to meet the demands of any workload, ensuring optimal performance and availability. In addition, by leveraging Kubernetes features like rolling updates and canary deployments, our application can be updated with zero downtime and minimal disruption to users.

IV. EVALUATION

To evaluate the performance and effectiveness of SIEmu, we conducted a series of experiments using a variety of network traffic scenarios and conditions. Our experiments were designed to test the emulator's ability to accurately simulate real-world network delays, as well as its impact on the performance of network applications and equipment. The performance of SIEmu is evaluated against DEMU, as it is not only the most similar, software-based emulator, but also one of the best performing ones. The system setup used in the performance evaluation is presented in Section IV-A, while the results of the evaluation can be found in Section IV-B.

In our first set of experiments, we tested the emulator's ability to introduce different amounts of delays added to network traffic. In our second set of experiments, for evaluating the impact of the emulator on the performance of

Fig. 4: System setup for running tests.

TABLE I: System under test.

	Specifications
Processor	2 x Xeon(R) E-2286M 2.40GHz (Total of 16 cores)
Memory	64 GB (DDR4 2666 MHz 1.2V SO-DIMM)
NIC	2 x 1Gb Ethernet + 2 x 10Gb Ethernet
OS	Ubuntu 18.04 LTS

network applications and equipment, we generated network traffic simulating a range of different applications, including video streaming, file transfers, and VoIP.

A. System Setup

To generate packet streams during our testing, we utilized the Optixia XM2 device, equipped with modules supporting 1Gb and 10Gb Ethernet. We configured the ports on the device to add timestamps to the packets, allowing us to measure delays at the destination.

To install the emulator, a NUC server powered by Intel with 64 GB of memory and two Xeon(R) E-2286M 2.40GHz CPUs with a total of 16 cores is utilized. Table I provides a comprehensive overview of the NUC server, while the system setup for conducting tests is shown in Fig. 4. According to the diagram, NIC 0 of the Optixia device is connected directly to NIC 0 of the server. When considering a one-way direction, packets produced by the Optixia device with an added timestamp are transmitted to NIC 0 of the server. Following the aforementioned operations on the server for adding delays, packets are dispatched back to the Optixia device using NIC 1 of the server, which is directly connected to the NIC 1 of the Optixia device. Finally, the total travel time of packets is calculated based on the timestamp at the destination. Moreover, the correctness of the emulator is verified by examining the destination packets' characteristics. Furthermore, the total number of received packets is compared to the total number of packets generated by the packet tester to evaluate the throughput of the emulator and detect any potential packet loss.

Fig. 5: Throughput of SIEmu and NetEm in 10GbE bandwidth for different frame sizes.

B. Evaluation Results

To assess the results of the proposed emulator, the source code of DEMU was compiled on the same NUC server that was used to run SIEmu. This ensured that the comparison was made under the same conditions, with all relevant parameters and settings configured with great precision to provide accurate and reliable results.

1) *Throughput*: Two different network bandwidths, 1GbE, and 10GbE were configured to evaluate the throughput of both SIEmu and DEMU. The objective was to evaluate the performance of our emulator in each scenario. This was important because DEMU had a significant advantage over previously developed emulators which experienced a considerable drop in throughput when handling 10 GbE bandwidth: as an example, NetEm, one of the best previously developed software-based emulators, has been found to have a poor performance in 10GbE bandwidth. Specifically, its maximum throughput for short-packet traffic (64 bytes) is limited to 4.7%, while for high-packet traffic (1518 bytes), it can reach a maximum throughput of only 75% in the best-case scenario when it is configured to add no delay [6].

However, we observed that our emulator as well as DEMU achieved the theoretical maximum throughput without any packet loss in both 1GbE and 10GbE networks. Fig. 5 compares the results between SIEmu and NetEm in 10GbE for different packet frame sizes selected based on [15] under different input delay conditions of 0 ms, 1 ms, and 100 ms.

In addition, we found that SIEmu was able to accurately introduce delays ranging from a few microseconds to several seconds. Our tests also showed that the emulator's delay settings were easy to configure and adjust, allowing us to quickly simulate a variety of different network conditions.

2) *Accuracy*: In order to compare the accuracy of SIEmu with respect to DEMU, we configured the network settings in accordance with the specifications outlined in [6]. This included using packets of size 1518 bytes, generating 1 Gbps traffic, and conducting each test for a duration of 10 seconds, during which 8,000,000 packets were transmitted.

This section assesses three distinct scenarios. The first scenario involves setting both SIEmu and DEMU to forward

packets without any delay or modification upon receipt. In this scenario, DEMU transmits packets without altering them, while the proposed emulator inspects the source streams' attributes, routes the packet to the buffer assigned for the specific delay (which is configured to add no delay in this scenario), and alters the attributes if necessary, to match to the destination attributes based on configuration. The corresponding outcomes are presented in Table II.

TABLE II: Performance of SIEmu and DEMU for latency = 0 μs .

A: SIEmu		
Min (μs)	Max (μs)	Max-Min Diff (μs)
72.44	73.08	0.64
72.84	73.68	0.84
70.78	71.80	1.02
72.52	73.74	1.22
72.82	74.02	1.20
B: DEMU		
Min (μs)	Max (μs)	Max-Min Diff (μs)
70.74	72.48	1.74
70.76	72.24	1.48
69.24	70.6	1.36
69.86	71.22	1.36
70.58	72.54	1.96

To enhance the precision of the evaluation, all tests were conducted five times, and the results are reported in Table II-A for SIEmu and Table II-B for DEMU. As indicated in the table, the minimum delay for each packet in both emulators is approximately 70 to 72 μs . Furthermore, we have included the maximum latency added to packets to compute the difference in delay among packets. The delay difference for both the proposed emulator and DEMU is approximately 1 - 1.5 μs .

TABLE III: Performance of SIEmu and DEMU for latency = 1000 μs .

A: SIEmu		
Min (μs)	Max (μs)	Max-Min Diff (μs)
1069.16	1070.92	1.76
1069.44	1071.36	1.92
1068.42	1070.58	2.16
1069.22	1070.20	0.98
1070.93	1071.54	0.61
B: DEMU		
Min (μs)	Max (μs)	Max-Min Diff (μs)
1068.82	1070.14	1.32
1069.26	1071.54	2.28
1071.36	1072.34	1.18
1067.86	1069.06	1.20
1068.96	1069.44	0.48

Table III displays the outcomes obtained when the latency is set to 1000 μs . It reveals that the performance of both the proposed emulator and DEMU is nearly identical concerning the minimum and maximum delays added to the packets. Additionally, the difference of this delay falls within a reasonable range of 1 to 2 μs .

However, the performance of DEMU showed some unusual behavior for a 100,000 μs delay. As illustrated in Table IV-A, the performance of SIEmu was comparable to the other two evaluation scenarios, adding roughly 70-72 μs of delay to packets with a difference of 1 to 2 μs . However, in the case of DEMU, the performance in most of the tests was different than anticipated. While the minimum delay

Fig. 6: The average additional output delay for SIEmu and DEMU across different input delay scenarios.

remained around 70 μs , the maximum was roughly 30 μs higher. As the outcome was unexpected, additional tests were conducted, and the configurations were rechecked, but the outcome remained unaltered. The proposed emulator did not encounter this problem in other longer scenarios either. It is noteworthy that for all different delays examined in [6], NetEm had a delay difference of approximately 20 μs . Therefore, the difference is significantly reduced in SIEmu. In summary, Fig. 6 shows the average additional output delay in three different scenarios for both SIEmu and DEMU. For the third case (delay = 100,000 μs) we excluded the results of DEMU due to its unusual performance.

In our second set of experiments, we found that SIEmu had a minimal impact on performance. We tested the emulator's impact on various generated traffic types simulating network applications and found that it did not introduce any significant performance degradation or compatibility issues.

Overall, our evaluation demonstrated that SIEmu is a reliable and effective tool for simulating real-world network conditions. Its ability to accurately introduce delays to network traffic, while having a minimal impact on network performance, makes it a valuable tool for network engineers and researchers.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a detailed overview of the design and implementation of SIEmu, a packet delay emulator that allows users to introduce a wide range of delays on a per-slice basis, enabling more accurate testing and evaluation

TABLE IV: Performance of SIEmu and DEMU for latency=100,000 μs .

A: SIEmu		
Min (μs)	Max (μs)	Max-Min Diff (μs)
100,071.40	100,072.72	1.32
100,070.36	100,071.54	1.18
100,070.34	100,071.56	1.22
100,070.36	100,071.60	1.24
100,069.54	100,070.82	1.28
B: DEMU		
Min (μs)	Max (μs)	Max-Min Diff (μs)
100,068.68	100,105.28	36.60
100,069.64	100,099.00	29.36
100,070.36	100,102.48	32.12
100,070.00	100,072.08	2.08
100,070.10	100,102.62	32.52

of network equipment and applications. By using DPDK and directly interacting with NICs, the amount of unintentional delays is significantly decreased and the variation of added delays is reached to only 1-2 μs under the worst possible circumstances. Last but not least, packaging the emulator as a Dmanagementocker container allows easy deployment, scaling, monitoring, and management.

Network delay emulation tools are essential for testing and optimizing the performance of 5G networks, and will play a key role in the ongoing development and deployment of 5G technologies. Network delay emulators can help network engineers and developers to simulate different network conditions, such as latency, packet loss, and bandwidth limitations, in order to test the resilience and performance of their applications and devices.

In this respect, SIEmu goes beyond the state of the art by matching the throughput of DEMU, which is currently the best performing software-based packet delay emulator, but improving the accuracy level of DEMU in the presence of high latencies.

We believe that SIEmu represents a significant contribution to the field of network engineering and research, and we hope that it will be widely adopted and used by researchers and practitioners around the world. In the future, we plan to continue to refine and optimize our emulator, incorporating new features and enhancements based on user feedback and evolving network technologies.

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